

1 Promoting replicability in developmental research through meta-analyses: Insights from
2 language acquisition research

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28

Abstract

29 Previous work suggests key factors for replicability, a necessary feature for theory building,
30 include statistical power and appropriate research planning. These factors are examined by
31 analyzing a collection of 12 standardized meta-analyses on language development between
32 birth and 5 years. With a median effect size of Cohen's $d = 0.45$ and typical sample size of
33 18 participants, most research is underpowered (range: 6%-99%; median 44%); and
34 calculating power based on seminal publications is not a suitable strategy. Method choice
35 can be improved, as shown in analyses on exclusion rates and effect size as a function of
36 method. The article ends with a discussion on how to increase replicability in both language
37 acquisition studies specifically and developmental research more generally.

38 *Keywords:* replicability, language acquisition, power, study planning, infancy

39 Word count: 6795

40 Promoting replicability in developmental research through meta-analyses: Insights from
41 language acquisition research

42 Empirical research is built on a never-ending conversation between theory and data,
43 between expectations and observations. Theories lead to new research questions and new
44 data in turn lead to refined theories. This process crucially relies on access to reliable
45 empirical data. Unfortunately, investigators of the scientific process have noted that the
46 assessment of the value of empirical data points can be biased by concerns about
47 publishability (Nosek, Spies, & Motyl, 2012), which often depends on the observation of
48 statistically significant and theoretically surprising outcomes (Sterling, Rosenbaum, &
49 Weinkam, 1995). Aiming for publishability has been suggested to lead to practices that
50 undermine the quality and reliability of data (Ioannidis, 2005; Smaldino & McElreath, 2016).
51 According to some, inappropriate research and reporting practices may be to blame for the
52 surprisingly high proportion of non-replicable findings in psychology (Simmons, Nelson, &
53 Simonsohn, 2011).

54 Replicability is crucial across domains; but developmental research may be particularly
55 vulnerable to unreliable findings: Collecting data from children is time-consuming, and thus
56 sample sizes are often small, studies are underpowered, and replications are rare. Small
57 sample sizes, and the ensuing lack of power, are a major risk factor for low replicability (e.g.,
58 Button et al., 2013). Meta-analysis – the set of statistical tools for aggregating quantitative
59 results across studies – can be a potent tool for addressing issues of replicability. Because no
60 single study is definitive, examining conclusions across studies will facilitate more robust
61 decision-making about the strength of the research literature. In addition, meta-analytic
62 tools can help identify and address issues in replicability by helping to assess weaknesses and
63 allow future studies to be planned more effectively through prospective power analysis.
64 Specifically, a meta-analysis can reveal the average effect size, sample size, and resulting
65 statistical power of a systematically assembled set of studies where a specific phenomenon

66 has been studied with a variety of methods, stimuli, and samples. Because each
67 meta-analysis typically addresses a single phenomenon – the underlying construct that is
68 supposed to elicit specific responses in laboratory studies – it is difficult to draw general
69 conclusions. To this end, we make use of MetaLab, a publicly available database of 12
70 standardized meta-analyses of language acquisition. MetaLab is a dynamic, continuously
71 growing database. At the time of writing, the available meta-analyses cover a variety of
72 behavioral and neuroimaging methods (11 in total) and participant ages (from newborns to
73 5-year-olds).

74 Since all meta-analyses in MetaLab address specific phenomena within language
75 acquisition, our empirical analyses are thus adjusted to the methods typically used in this
76 subfield of developmental research. Nonetheless, our analyses and recommendations are
77 relevant beyond the scope of language acquisition research. Crucially, we investigate key
78 study design choices that will be relevant to developmental research at large: sample size
79 (and the ensuing statistical power when effect size is held constant) and method (i.e.,
80 paradigms used to tap into the same phenomenon). Furthermore, since our work is
81 comprised of open data and scripts, accompanied by extensive educational materials, and we
82 use open source software (specifically R; R Core Team, 2016), our approach can easily be
83 extended to other domains of child development research. We strongly encourage fellow
84 researchers to build similar collections of meta-analyses describing and quantifying
85 phenomena in their respective sub-domain.

86 **The meta-analyses in MetaLab**

87 Before laying out the key concerns for replicability that are more broadly relevant, it
88 may be useful to give a brief overview of our dataset: Each included meta-analysis focuses on
89 one specific phenomenon, and collectively they cover a wide range of linguistic levels, from
90 phonetics (e.g., native vowel discrimination; Tsuji & Cristia, 2014) to pragmatics (e.g.,

91 pointing and vocabulary; Colonnese, Stams, Koster, & Nool, 2010) and a range of designs
92 and methods. All but one meta-analysis aggregate experimental studies on the strength of
93 processing of a particular experimentally-manipulated stimulus contrast. The one exception
94 is a meta-analysis containing correlations between toddlers' pointing and vocabulary size
95 measured concurrently (Colonnese et al., 2010). Depending on the meta-analysis and thus
96 phenomenon in question, studies either bear on knowledge acquired outside the lab to tap
97 into continued real-life acquisition processes, or are based on laboratory-based training,
98 typically to isolate a proposed learning mechanism. Examples of the former are native and
99 non-native vowel discrimination (Tsuji & Cristia, 2014) and online recognition of known
100 words (Frank, Lewis, & MacDonald, 2016); the latter is exemplified by learning sound
101 categories and sound sequences in the lab after short exposure to artificial mini-languages
102 (Cristia, 2017). The dependent variable in all these studies is based on continuous response
103 data, such as looking time; either measured within participants in reaction to two conditions
104 or across participant groups receiving different exposures.

105 Children in our data are aged 0-5 years. In our analyses, we take into account
106 participant age for both practical and theoretical reasons. On the practical side, we expect
107 an effect of infant age based on three aspects of child development research. Firstly, younger
108 infants may be more difficult to recruit and test, thereby increasing measurement noise and
109 leading to smaller effect sizes in younger, compared to older, cohorts. Secondly, tasks and
110 designs might vary as a function of participant age. This factor does not allow us to make a
111 precise prediction with respect to age trends, but does encourage an investigation of research
112 practices and effect sizes as a function of age. Thirdly, even if our tests are conceptually
113 associated to early language acquisition, childhood is a time of rapid cognitive development
114 of various cognitive skills ranging from selective attention to working memory (Lerner, Liben,
115 & Mueller, 2015), which could impact laboratory performance and would be reflected in the
116 strength, and even direction, of an effect (e.g., Hunter & Ames, 1988).

117 From a theoretical standpoint, the phenomena targeted by the meta-analyses currently
118 in MetaLab are expected to show changes with age. In general, this change is in a positive
119 direction: Younger participants should show smaller effects than older ones because they are
120 not yet as experienced with, and proficient in, their native language, and thus we expect
121 them to improve in most linguistic skills, such as native vowel discrimination, word form
122 recognition, and word to meaning mapping. The one exception in our collection is
123 non-native vowel discrimination, an ability that should and does decrease as infants tune
124 into their native language (Tsuji & Cristia, 2014). For a number of phenomena theoretical
125 predictions are not straightforward (e.g., a preference for infant- over adult-directed speech is
126 thought to increase in the first few months as children accumulate experience with this
127 affective register, but could have been predicted to eventually decrease due to novelty
128 preferences; Hunter & Ames, 1988).

129 In sum, the set of meta-analysis we use covers a wide range of phenomena and
130 methods, increasing the likelihood that our conclusions are not specific to language
131 acquisition. Moreover, key concerns for replicability, as laid out in the next section, are likely
132 to apply and take effect across sub-disciplines of developmental research. We return to the
133 generalizability of our findings in the discussion.

134 **Key concerns for replicable research in developmental science**

135 **Statistical power.** In this section we review potential hindrances to developmental
136 research being robust and reproducible, and briefly describe how we assess current practices
137 in terms of sampling decisions and resulting power. All of these descriptions are by necessity
138 brief; for extended discussions we provide references to suitable readings.

139 In the null-hypothesis significance testing framework, statistical power refers to the
140 probability of detecting an effect and correctly rejecting the null hypothesis if an effect is

141 indeed present in a population. Power is dependent on the underlying effect size and the
142 sample size. Of course, low power is problematic because it increases the likelihood of type-II
143 errors (i.e., failure to find a significant result when there is an effect present in the
144 population). It has become increasingly clear, however, that low power can also increase the
145 frequency of type-I errors (false positives), as the effects reported in such cases will be
146 overestimating the true effect (Button et al., 2013; see also Ioannidis, 2005; Simmons et al.,
147 2011). This fact makes appropriate planning for future research more difficult, as sample
148 sizes will be too small, increasing the likelihood of null results due to insensitive research
149 designs rather than the absence of the underlying effect. In addition, this issue is a serious
150 hindrance to work building on seminal studies, including replications and extensions.

151 Underpowered studies pose an additional and very serious problem for developmental
152 researchers that interpret significant findings as indicating that a skill is “present” and
153 nonsignificant findings as a sign that it is “absent”. In fact, even in the most rigorous study
154 design and execution, null results will occur regularly. Consider a series of studies with 80%
155 power (a number typically deemed sufficient), where every fifth result will be a false negative,
156 that means it will not reflect that there is a true effect present in the population. This
157 observation was recently demonstrated by Oakes (2017) by using data from a high-powered
158 looking time study.

159 To investigate current practices in our sample, we compute typical power per
160 phenomenon, based on meta-analytic effect sizes and typical sample size (Button et al.,
161 2013). The logic of this analysis is as follows: Although we cannot know the exact power of
162 any given experiment (because we do not know the true underlying effect), the meta-analytic
163 effect size represents our best guess; thus, the median power for a phenomenon is the power
164 of the median sample size with the meta-analytic effect size. We next explore which effect
165 sizes would be detectable with the sample sizes typically tested in language acquisition
166 research. We additionally investigate how researchers might determine sample sizes using a

167 different heuristic, namely following the largest effect size reported in the first paper on a
168 given phenomenon.

169 **Method choice.** Improving procedures in developmental research can be considered
170 both an economical and ethical necessity, because developmental populations are difficult to
171 recruit and test. A further complication is that a non-negligible proportion are excluded
172 because they fail to comply, finish the study, or conform to other data quality criteria the
173 researcher sets (e.g., a minimum looking time during test trials). For this reason,
174 developmentalists often “tweak” paradigms and develop new ones with the aim of obtaining
175 a clearer signal and/or control the exclusion rate. Emerging technologies, such as
176 eye-tracking and tablets, have consequently been eagerly adopted (Frank, Sugarman,
177 Horowitz, Lewis, & Yurovsky, 2016; Gredebäck, Johnson, & Hofsten, 2009).

178 Thus, it remains an open question to what extent the different methods within
179 developmental research lead to comparable results. Some may be more robust, but it is
180 difficult to extract such information based on comparisons of individual studies that use
181 different materials and test various age groups (cf. the large-scale experimental approach by
182 ManyBabies Collaborative, 2017). Aggregating over results via meta-analytic tools allows us
183 to assess to what extent methods differ in their associated exclusion rate as well as to extract
184 general patterns of higher or lower noise via the comparison of effect sizes since the latter are
185 directly affected by the variance of the measurement.

186 **Questionable research practices.** Undisclosed flexibility during data collection
187 and analysis is a problem independent of the availability of various methods to conduct
188 developmental studies. One salient example is flexible stopping rules, where the decision to
189 stop or continue testing depends on the result of a statistical test. Though this practice
190 might seem innocuous and geared towards “bringing out” an effect the researcher believes is
191 real, it increases the likelihood of obtaining a “significant” outcome well beyond the expected
192 5%, effectively rendering p values and the notion of statistical significance meaningless

193 (Ioannidis, 2005; Simmons et al., 2011).

194 It is typically not possible to assess whether undisclosed flexibility during data
195 collection (or analysis) led to a false positive in a given report. However, we can measure
196 “symptoms” in a whole literature. We focus in this paper on flexibility in stopping data
197 collection, a practice that was found to be present, but not predominant, in infancy research
198 in a recent anonymous survey (Eason, Hamlin, & Sommerville, 2017). Since our data span
199 over 44 years (publications date range from 1973 to 2017), it might be the case that recent
200 discussions of best practices have improved lab procedures, but older reports could still have
201 applied this seemingly innocuous practice of adding participants to “bring out” the effect of
202 interest.

203 **Summary of research goals**

204 We will use a collection of meta-analyses in language acquisition to describe the
205 current state of this field in terms of effect sizes, sample sizes, and, relatedly, statistical
206 power. We take into account the fact that the meta-analyses bear on diverse phenomena,
207 studied in different age groups and with a variety of methods and sample sizes, and that
208 combinations of these factors will likely affect both effect size and exclusion rates. While we
209 consider the conceptual structure imposed by the fact that the meta-analyses bear on
210 language acquisition, our overarching goal is to exemplify how these analyses can be carried
211 out to describe any subfield of developmental research and to give concrete recommendations
212 and tools to increase replicability within the developmental sciences.

213

Methods

214 All scripts used in this paper and information how to obtain the source data from
215 MetaLab are shared on Open Science Framework at

216 https://osf.io/uhv3d/?view_only=5a3a3412ea814e3393728395971ee292.

217 **Data**

218 The data presented and analyzed here are part of a standardized collection of
219 meta-analyses (MetaLab), and are freely available via the companion website at
220 <http://metalab.stanford.edu>. Currently, MetaLab contains 12 meta-analyses, where core
221 parts of each meta-analysis are standardized to allow for the computation of common effect
222 size estimates and for analyses that span across different phenomena. These standardized
223 variables include study descriptors (such as citation and peer review status), participant
224 characteristics (including mean age and native language), methodological information (e.g.,
225 what dependent variable was measured), and information necessary to compute effect sizes
226 (number of participants, if available means and standard deviations of the dependent
227 measure, otherwise test statistics of the key hypothesis test, such as t values or F scores).

228 Meta-analyses were contributed to MetaLab directly ($n=10$) or they were extracted
229 from previously published meta-analyses related to language development ($n=2$; Colonna et
230 al., 2010; Dunst, Gorman, & Hamby, 2012). In the former case, the meta-analysis authors
231 attempted to document as much detail as possible for each entered experiment (note that a
232 paper can contain many experiments, as shown in Table 1), as recommended for reproducible
233 and dynamic meta-analyses (Tsuji, Bergmann, & Cristia, 2014). Detailed descriptions of all
234 phenomena covered by MetaLab, including which papers and other sources have been
235 considered, can be found at <http://metalab.stanford.edu>.

236 **Statistical approach**

237 As dependent measure, we report Cohen's d , a standardized effect size based on
238 comparing sample means and their variance. Effect size was calculated when possible from

239 means and standard deviations across designs with the appropriate formulae (Dunlap,
240 Cortina, Vaslow, & Burke, 1996; Lipsey & Wilson, 2001; Morris & DeShon, 2002;
241 Viechtbauer, 2010). When these data were not available,, we computed effect size based on
242 the test statistics used to asses the main hypothesis, more precisely t values or F . We also
243 computed effect size variance, which allowed us to weight each effect size when aggregating
244 across studies. The variance is mainly determined by the number of participants; intuitively,
245 effect sizes based on larger samples will be assigned more weight. Note that for research
246 designs testing the same participants in two conditions (for example measuring reactions of
247 the same infants to infant- and adult-directed speech), correlations between those two
248 measures are needed to estimate the effect size variance. This measure is usually not
249 reported, despite being necessary for effect size calculation (note: publishing guidelines
250 require the reporting of correlations; American Psychological Association, 2001). Some
251 correlations could be obtained through direct contact with the original authors (see e.g.,
252 Bergmann & Cristia, 2016), the remaining ones were imputed. We report details of effect
253 size calculation in the supplementary materials and make available all scripts used in the
254 present paper. Excluded as outliers were effect sizes more than three standard deviations
255 away from the median effect size within each meta-analysis ($n=12$).

256 **Meta-analytic model.** Meta-analytic effect sizes were estimated using
257 random-effect models where effect sizes were weighted by their inverse variance. We further
258 used a multilevel approach, which takes into account not only the effect sizes and variance of
259 single studies, but also that effect sizes from the same paper will be based on more similar
260 studies than effect sizes from different papers (Konstantopoulos, 2011). When analyzing data
261 from multiple meta-analyses, we nested paper within meta-analysis to account for the fact
262 that studies within meta-analyses will be more similar to each other. We relied on the
263 implementation in the R (R Core Team, 2016) package metafor (Viechtbauer, 2010).

264 **Power calculation.** We calculated typical power using the pwr package (Champely,
265 2015) based on the meta-analytical effect size and the median number of participants within
266 each meta-analysis. For targeted analyses of the power of seminal papers, we extracted the
267 largest effect size and used this value for power calculation, taking in both cases the median
268 number of participants in a meta-analysis into account (for a similar approach see e.g.,
269 Button et al., 2013).

270 **Results**

271 **Sample size and statistical power**

272 Table 1 provides a summary of typical sample sizes and effect sizes per meta-analysis.
273 We remind the reader that recommendations are for power to be above 80%, which means
274 that four out of five studies show a significant outcome for an effect truly present in the
275 population.

276 As could be expected, sample sizes are small across all meta-analyses, with the overall
277 median in our data being 18 infants or paired observations (i.e. 36 participants in total in a
278 between-participant design). Effect sizes predominantly fall into ranges of small to medium
279 effects, as defined by Cohen (Cohen, 1988). The overall median effect size of all data
280 analyzed here is Cohen's $d = 0.45$. As a result of those two factors, studies are typically
281 severely under-powered. Assuming a paired t-test (within-participant designs are the most
282 frequent in the present data), observed power is at 44% (for independent samples, observed
283 power is at 26%).

284 With the observed sample size, it is possible to detect an effect in 80% of all studies
285 when Cohen's $d = 0.70$; in other words, this sample size would be appropriate when
286 investigating a medium to large effect. When comparing two independent groups, the effect
287 size that would be detectable with a sample size of 18 participants per group increases to

288 Cohen's $d = 0.96$, a large effect that is rarely observed as meta-analytic effect size in the
289 present collection of developmental meta-analyses.

290 Inversely, to detect the typical effect of Cohen's $d = 0.45$ with 80% power, studies
291 would have to test 40 participants in a paired design; 22 more than are included on average.
292 For a between-participant design, a study with 80% power would require testing 77 infants
293 per group, over four times the typical sample size we encounter here. This disparity between
294 observed and necessary sample size varies greatly across meta-analyses, leading to drastic
295 differences in observed power to detect the main effect. While studies on phonotactic
296 learning and word segmentation apparently typically are dramatically underpowered (with
297 observed power being under 10%), experiments on pointing and vocabulary, gaze following,
298 and online word recognition are very well powered (92%, 95%, and 99%, respectively).

299 We find no strong linear link between participant age and sample size on the level of
300 meta-analyses (Table 1). However, effect sizes and consequently power increase with median
301 participant age. Most saliently, the only three meta-analyses with power over 80%, pointing
302 and vocabulary, gaze following, and online word recognition, typically test participants older
303 than one year.

304 **Seminal papers as basis for sample size planning.** As Table 1 shows,
305 experimenters only rarely include a sufficient number of participants to observe a given effect
306 – assuming the meta-analytic estimate is accurate. It might, however, be possible, that power
307 has been determined based on a seminal paper to be replicated and expanded. Initial reports
308 tend to overestimate effect sizes (Jennions & Møller, 2002), possibly explaining the lack of
309 observed power in the subsequent literature.

310 For each meta-analysis, we extracted the oldest paper and the largest effect size
311 reported therein and re-calculated power accordingly, using the median sample size of the
312 same meta-analysis (see Table 2). The largest effect size per paper was chosen because many

313 seminal studies contain at least one null result in a control condition that delineates the
314 limitations of a given phenomenon (for example that older children succeed at a task that
315 their younger peers fail). Thus, it is unlikely that the researchers following up on that work
316 aim for the median or mean effect size.

317 In some cases, such as native and non-native vowel discrimination, as shown in Table 2,
318 sample size choices match well with the oldest report. The difference in power, noted in the
319 last column, can be substantial, with native vowel discrimination and phonotactic learning
320 being the two most salient examples. Here, sample sizes match well with the oldest report
321 and studies would be appropriately powered if this estimate were representative of the true
322 effect. In four meta-analyses neither the seminal paper nor meta-analytic effect size seem to
323 be a useful basis for sample size decisions. Since these numbers are based on the largest
324 effect of a seminal paper, all power estimations (but also differences in meta-analytic effect
325 sizes) would be smaller, meaning that sample sizes are less appropriate than implied by the
326 column denoting power based on the seminal paper in Table 2.

327 **Method choice**

328 **Exclusion rates across methods.** In most of the analyzed meta-analyses, multiple
329 methods were used to tap into the phenomenon in question. Choosing a robust method can
330 help increase power, because more precise measurements lead to larger effect sizes due to
331 reduced measurement variance and thus require fewer participants to be tested to conduct
332 appropriately-powered studies. However, the number of participants relates to the final
333 sample and not how many participants had to be invited into the lab. We thus first quantify
334 whether methods differ in their typical exclusion rate, as economic considerations might
335 drive method choice. To this end we consider all methods which have more than 10
336 associated effect sizes and for which information on the number of excluded participants was
337 reported and entered in the meta-analyses. We note that this is exclusion rate, rather than

338 fussout or dropout rates, because it represents the number excluded considering all criteria,
339 including data quality criteria such as a minimum looking time. We chose this variable for
340 practical reasons, as overall exclusion rates are more frequently reported than the number of
341 participants who did not complete the experiment. The following analyses cover 6 methods
342 and 224 effect sizes.

343 The results of a linear mixed effects model predicting exclusion rate by method and
344 mean participant age (while controlling for the different underlying effect sizes per
345 meta-analysis) are summarized in Table 3 and visualized in Figure 1. The results show
346 significant variation across methods, and a tendency toward higher exclusion rates for older
347 participants, with some interaction with method.

348 **Effect sizes as a function of method.** We built a meta-analytic model with
349 Cohen's d as the dependent variable, and method and mean age centered as independent
350 variables, which we allowed to interact. The model includes the variance of d for sampling
351 variance, aa nested random effect of paper (inner random effect) within meta-analysis (outer
352 random effect). We limited this analysis to the same methods that we investigated in the
353 section on exclusion rates to be able to observe possible links between effect size and
354 exclusion rate in methods. The model results in Table 4 show significant variation in effect
355 sizes across methods, age, and some interaction of method and age.

356 **Questionable research practices**

357 In the final set of analyses, we assess the relation between absolute observed effect sizes
358 in single studies and the associated sample size. The rationale behind this analysis is simple:
359 The smaller the effect size in a particular study (bear in mind that we assume that
360 experiments sample from a distribution around the population effect), the larger the sample
361 needed for a significant p value. If sample size decisions are made before data collection and

362 all results are published, we expect no relation between observed effect size and sample size.
363 If, on the contrary, authors continue to add infants to achieve significance (Begg &
364 Mazumdar, 1994), there should be a negative correlation between sample size and effect size.

365 We illustrate the link between effect size and sample size, separated by meta-analysis,
366 in Figure 3. The statistical test results for each meta-analysis can be found in Table 5. Four
367 meta-analyses show a significant negative relation between sample size and effect size,
368 consistent with bias; two of them assess infants' ability to discriminate vowels, one bears on
369 word segmentation, and one tests whether children use mutual exclusivity during word
370 learning. The last case might be driven by a single high-powered study with an atypical
371 developmental range (Frank et al., 2016). We further observe an unexpected positive
372 correlation between sample size and observed effect size in the meta-analysis on infant
373 directed speech preference, which we discuss below.

374

Discussion

375 In this paper, we made use of a collection of 12 standardized meta-analyses to assess
376 typical effect sizes, sample size, power, and methodological choices that are currently
377 common in research on language development. With an average effect size of Cohen's $d =$
378 0.45 and a typical sample size of only 18 participants per cell, observed power is at 44%.

379 The lack of power is particularly salient for phenomena typically tested on younger
380 children, because sample sizes and effect sizes are both small (the one exception for research
381 topics tested mainly with participants younger than one year is non-native vowel
382 discrimination, which can be attributed to a large meta-analytic effect size estimate rather
383 than larger samples). Phenomena studied among older children tended to yield larger effects,
384 and here some studies turn out to be high-powered (e.g., online word recognition). Both
385 observations are first indicators that effect size estimates might not be considered when

386 determining sample size, as power of 99% would suggest the sample was unnecessarily large
387 for the effect under study (see Table 1). However, it is possible that, in addition to testing a
388 main effect (such as whether children recognize a given word online) these high-powered
389 studies also investigated interactions (i.e., factors modulating this ability). As a consequence,
390 studies might be powered appropriately since an interaction effect will be more difficult to
391 detect than a main effect. The possibility that follow-up studies are looking for moderators
392 and thus test interaction effects means that the 44% average power observed above would be
393 an overestimate.

394 We next investigated the possibility that researchers base their sample size on the
395 highest effect size reported in the seminal paper of their research topic. We find that even
396 under this assumption, the surveyed research would largely be underpowered. Moreover, this
397 strategy would likely not provide sufficient power with respect to meta-analytic effect sizes,
398 as early explorations will tend to overestimate effect sizes (Jennions & Møller, 2002). In
399 short, studies are habitually underpowered because sample sizes typically remain close to
400 what can be called a “field standard” of 15 to 20 participants (see Table 1 in this paper and
401 Oakes, 2017).

402 Conducting studies with sample sizes based on “field standards” is highly problematic
403 for several reasons. First, many studies will not yield significant outcomes despite the
404 presence of a real, but small effect. Researchers might thus be inclined to conclude that an
405 ability is absent in a population (see below for an in-depth discussion of this topic), or they
406 may refrain from publishing their data altogether. If an underpowered study is published
407 because the outcome is significant, this study will overestimate the size of the underlying
408 effect, thereby adding biased results to the available literature (and thus further biasing any
409 meta-analytic effect size estimate; Sterling et al., 1995; Yarkoni, 2009), as well as reinforcing
410 the practice of sampling too few participants. At worst, this practice can lead to the
411 perpetuation of a false hypothesis (for an example, albeit from non-developmental research,

412 consider the meta-analysis of romantic priming by Shanks et al., 2015).

413 We investigated the possibility that researchers selectively add participants to obtain a
414 significant result through the relation between observed effect size and sample size. We
415 observed that in four meta-analyses effect sizes were significantly negatively correlated with
416 sample sizes, which might be an indication of questionable research practices. At the same
417 time we found a (numerically) positive correlation in the meta-analysis on infant-directed
418 speech preference, an unexpected result as it means that larger sample sizes tend to be found
419 in experiments with larger effects. One possible reason for the latter result might be specific
420 to this dataset: perhaps older infants are both easier to test and have greater preferences for
421 infant-directed speech.

422 For the four observed negative correlations, alternative explanations to questionable
423 research practices are possible: As soon as researchers are aware that they are measuring a
424 more subtle effect and adjust sample sizes accordingly, we expect to observe this negative
425 correlation. Consider for example vowel discrimination, which can be studied with very
426 distinct vowel-pairs such as in “bit” and “but”, or with subtler contrasts like in “bat” and
427 “bet”. In fact, in the presence of consequent and accurate a priori power calculations, a
428 negative correlation between sample size and effect size must be observed. However, our
429 previous analyses indicate that power is not considered when making sample size decisions.

430 **Concrete recommendations for developmental scientists**

431 In this section, we move from a description of current practices to suggestions aimed at
432 improving the reproducibility of developmental research. We generalize to developmental
433 studies at large because there is reason to believe that other sub-domains in the study of
434 infant and child development may be subject to the same issues we outlined in the
435 introduction.

436 **1. Calculate power prospectively.** We found that most studies testing infants
437 and toddlers are severely underpowered, even when aiming to detect only a main effect.
438 Interactions will show smaller effect sizes and thus will be even harder to detect. Further,
439 power varies greatly across phenomena, which is mainly due to differences in effect sizes.
440 Sample sizes are not adjusted accordingly, but remain close to the typical sample size of 18.

441 Our first recommendation is thus to assess in advance how many participants would be
442 needed to detect a minimal effect size of interest (for a more detailed discussion and practical
443 recommendations see Lakens & Evers, 2014). Note that we based our power estimations on
444 whole meta-analyses, an analysis approach most suitable to making general statements about
445 a research field at large. It might, however, be the case that specific studies might want to
446 base their power estimates on a subset of effect sizes to match age group and method. Both
447 factors can, as we showed in our results, influence the to-be-expected effect size. To facilitate
448 such analyses, all meta-analyses are shared on MetaLab along with the available details
449 about procedure and measurements (see also Tsuji et al., 2014).

450 In lines of research where no meta-analytic effect size estimate is available - either
451 because it is a novel phenomenon being investigated or simply due to the absence of
452 meta-analyses - we recommend considering typical effect sizes for the method used and the
453 age group being tested. This paper is a first step towards establishing such measures, but
454 more efforts and investigations are needed for robust estimates (Cristia, Seidl, Singh, &
455 Houston, 2016).

456 **2. Carefully consider method choice.** One way to increase power is the use of
457 more sensitive measurements; and we do find striking differences between methods. On the
458 practical side, exclusion rates varied a great deal (with medians between 5.9% and 45%).
459 Interestingly, the methods with somewhat lower exclusion rates (central fixation and
460 headturn preference procedure) are among the most frequent ones in our data and certainly
461 more frequent than those with higher exclusion rates. The proportion of participants that

462 can be retained might thus inform researchers' choice. This observation points to the
463 previously mentioned limitations regarding the participant pool, as more participants will
464 have to be tested to arrive at the same final sample size. High exclusion rates can also be
465 offset by high effect sizes; as can be seen when comparing conditioned headturn in Figures 1
466 and 2, while exclusion rates are around 30-50%, effect sizes are above 1. The second method
467 with high exclusion rates, stimulus alternation, in contrast, does not fall into this pattern of
468 high exclusion rates coinciding with high effect sizes. A possible interpretation of this finding
469 is that some methods, which have higher exclusion rates, generate higher effect sizes due to
470 decreased noise (e.g., by excluding participants who are not on task). However, there is an
471 important caveat: Studies with fewer participants (thanks to higher exclusion rates) are
472 imprecise, and thus it is more likely that significant results overestimate the underlying effect.

473 Nevertheless, when possible, it seems important to consider the paradigm being used,
474 and possibly use a more sensitive way of measuring infants' capabilities. One reason that
475 researchers do not appear to choose the most robust methods might again be due to a lack of
476 consideration of meta-analytic effect size estimates, which in turn might be (partially) due to
477 a lack of information on (how to interpret) effect size estimates and lack of experience using
478 them for study planning (Mills-Smith, Spangler, Panneton, & Fritz, 2015). We thus
479 recommend to change this practice and take into account the possibility that different
480 methods' sensitivity is reflected in effect size. Efforts to estimate the impact of method
481 choice experimentally through large-scale replications will likely be informative in this quest
482 (Frank et al., 2017).

483 **3. Report all data.** A possible reason for prospective power calculations and
484 meta-analyses being rare lies in the availability of data in published reports. Despite
485 longstanding recommendations to move beyond the persistent focus on *p* values (such as
486 American Psychological Association, 2001), a shift towards effect sizes or even the reporting
487 of them has not (yet) been widely adopted (Mills-Smith et al., 2015).

488 In addition, in cases where effect sizes are not mentioned, current reporting standards
489 make it difficult - at times even impossible - to derive effect sizes from the published
490 literature. For example, for within-participant measures it is necessary to report the
491 correlation between repeated measures associated to the paired conditions (most commonly a
492 treatment and control condition). However, this correlation is habitually not reported and
493 has to be obtained via direct contact with study authors (see for example Bergmann &
494 Cristia, 2016) or estimated (as described in Black & Bergmann, 2017). In addition, reporting
495 (as well as analysis) of results is generally highly variable, with raw means and standard
496 deviations not being available for all papers.

497 We suggest reporting the following information, in line with current guidelines: means
498 and standard deviations of dependent measures being statistically analyzed (for
499 within-participant designs with two dependent variables, correlations between the two should
500 be added), test statistic, exact p value (when computed), and effect sizes (for example
501 Cohen's d as used in the present paper) where possible. Such a standard not only follows
502 extant guidelines but also creates coherence across papers and reports, thus improving clarity
503 (Mills-Smith et al., 2015). A step further would be the supplementary sharing of all
504 anonymized results on the participant level, thus allowing for the computations necessary for
505 meta-analyses, and opening the door for other types of cumulative analyses.

506 **3. Increase the use and availability of meta-analyses.** Conducting a
507 meta-analysis is a laborious process, particularly according to common practice where only a
508 few people do the work, with little support tools and educational materials available. The
509 workload associated with conducting a meta-analysis may thus appear (and perhaps even be)
510 much larger than that associated with a publication containing original data or with a
511 qualitative review, making meta-analyses less attractive than the latter two for individuals.
512 Moreover, the benefits of meta-analyses for the field, for instance the possibility of
513 conducting power analyses, are often neither evident nor accessible to individual researchers,

514 as the data are not shared and traditional meta-analyses remain static after publication,
515 aging quickly as new results emerge (Tsuji et al., 2014).

516 To support the improvement of current practices, we propose making meta-analyses
517 available in the form of ready-to-use online tools, dynamic reports, and as raw data. These
518 different levels allow researchers with varying interests and expertise to make the best use of
519 the extant records on language development, including study planning, by choosing robust
520 methods and appropriate sample sizes. An additional advantage of using meta-analysis when
521 interpreting single results is that researchers can easily check whether their result falls within
522 the expected range of outcomes for their research question - indicating whether or not a
523 potential moderator influenced the result.

524 Meta-analyses can also be useful for theory building. Indeed, aggregating over many
525 data points allows us to trace the emergence of abilities over time, as well as quantify their
526 growth, and identify possible developmental trajectories. A demonstration is given in the
527 work of Tsuji and Cristia (2014), where mainstream descriptions of development for native
528 and non-native vowel discrimination could be confirmed. Contrastingly, Bergmann and
529 Cristia (2016) showed that word segmentation from native speech does not follow the
530 typically assumed developmental trajectory (for a recent discussion of both meta-analyses see
531 Bergmann, Tsuji, & Cristia, 2017). As a consequence, meta-analytic investigations lead to
532 more refined, or even reconsidered, theoretical accounts of child development, bolstered with
533 a better estimate of the timeline for phenomena of interest (see also Lewis et al., 2017).

534 **5. Use cumulative evidence to decide whether skills are “absent” or not.**
535 Developmental researchers often interpret both significant and nonsignificant findings,
536 particularly to establish a timeline tracing when skills emerge. This approach is problematic
537 for multiple reasons, as we mentioned in the Introduction. Disentangling whether a
538 nonsignificant finding indicates the absence of a skill, random measurement noise, or the lack
539 of experimental power to detect this skill reliably and with statistical support, is in fact

540 impossible based on p values. Further, we want to caution researchers against interpreting
541 the difference between significant and nonsignificant findings without statistically assessing it
542 first (Nieuwenhuis, Forstmann, & Wagenmakers, 2011). As mentioned, meta-analyses provide
543 a more principled way for assessing statistically whether age explains significant proportions
544 of the variance in observed effects. Moreover, this technique can also help with cases where
545 the absence of an effect is incorrectly inferred from a string of nonsignificant, potentially
546 underpowered, studies, as recently demonstrated by Vadillo, Konstantinidis, and Shanks
547 (2016). In their study, the authors pooled null results that had been taken as evidence for an
548 absent effect, and demonstrated the meta-analytic effect size estimate was Cohen's $d = .3$
549 (an effect that happens to be larger than that found in some meta-analyses included here).

550 **Future directions**

551 The present analyses can be expanded and improved in a number of ways. First, this
552 collection of meta-analyses does not represent an exhaustive survey of phenomena in
553 language acquisition, let alone developmental research. Particularly, topics typically
554 investigated in younger children are over-represented. Future analyses of a possible relation
555 between age, effect size, and sample size would thus benefit from a larger sample of
556 meta-analyses. A second potential impediment to generalizing from the presented findings to
557 developmental research at large is the fact that we focused on language acquisition research.
558 As there is no a priori reason to expect that sample sizes and effect sizes are particularly low
559 in this sub-domain of developmental science, and because most methods are used across
560 fields, we expect that the results and recommendations are relevant to researchers working in
561 other domains. However, to be able to make such claims with more certainty, standardized
562 collections of meta-analyses on phenomena in different sub-domains of developmental
563 research are needed. We strongly encourage such endeavours, and have made all materials
564 openly available and provided substantial documentation to expand this approach beyond

565 language acquisition studies.

566 **Conclusion**

567 We have showcased the use of standardized collections of meta-analyses for the
568 diagnosis of (potential) issues in developmental research, using early language acquisition as
569 a case study. Our results point to an overall lack of consideration of meta-analytic effect size
570 in study planning, leading to habitually under-powered studies. In addition, method choice
571 and participant age modulate effect size; we here provide first indicators of the importance of
572 both factors in study design. To improve the replicability of developmental research, and as
573 a consequence the empirical basis on which theories of development are built, we strongly
574 recommend an increased use of effect sizes and meta-analytic tools, including prospective
575 power calculations.

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Table 1

Descriptions of meta-analyses. Age is reported in months, sample size is based on the median in a given meta-analysis, effect size is reported as meta-analytic weighted median Cohen’s d, and average power is computed based on meta-analytic effect size estimate Cohen’s d and median sample size.

Meta-Analysis	Age	Sample Size	N Effect Sizes	N Papers	Effect Size (SE)	Power
Gaze following	14 (3-24)	23 (12-63)	32	11	1.08 (0.16)	0.99
IDS preference	4 (0-9)	20 (10-60)	48	16	0.73 (0.13)	0.99
Concept-label advantage	12 (4-18)	13 (9-32)	48	15	0.45 (0.08)	0.99
Mutual exclusivity	24 (15-60)	16 (8-72)	58	19	0.81 (0.14)	0.99
Online word recognition	18 (15-30)	25 (16-95)	14	6	1.24 (0.26)	0.99
Phonotactic learning	11 (4-16)	18 (8-40)	47	15	0.12 (0.07)	0.99
Pointing and vocabulary	22 (9-34)	24.5 (6-50)	12	12	0.98 (0.18)	0.99
Sound symbolism	8 (4-38)	20 (11-40)	44	11	0.22 (0.11)	0.99
Statistical sound learning	8 (2-11)	15.5 (5-34)	19	11	0.29 (0.14)	0.99
Native vowel discrim.	7 (0-30)	12 (6-50)	112	29	0.69 (0.09)	0.99
Non-native vowel discrim.	8 (2-18)	16 (8-30)	46	14	0.79 (0.24)	0.99
Word segmentation	8 (6-25)	20 (4-64)	284	68	0.16 (0.03)	0.99

Table 2

For each meta-analysis, largest effect size Cohen's d and derived power based on the seminal paper, along with meta-analytic and seminal paper effect size.

Meta-Analysis	Effect Size Seminal Paper	Effect Size Overall	Sample Size	Power Seminal Paper
Statistical sound learning	-0.24	0.29	15.50	
Word segmentation	0.56	0.16	20.00	
Mutual exclusivity	0.70	0.81	16.00	
Concept-label advantage	0.86	0.45	13.00	
Pointing and vocabulary	0.65	0.98	24.50	
Non-native vowel discrim.	1.02	0.79	16.00	
Phonotactic learning	0.98	0.12	18.00	
Sound symbolism	0.95	0.22	20.00	
Online word recognition	0.89	1.24	25.00	
Gaze following	1.29	1.08	23.00	
Native vowel discrim.	1.87	0.69	12.00	
IDS preference	2.39	0.73	20.00	

Table 3

Linear mixed effects model predicting exclusion rate by method and participant age while accounting for the specific phenomenon.

	Est.	SE Est	t	p
Intercept	31.17	4.48	6.96	4e-12
CondHT	31.06	5.73	5.42	6e-08
FC	-26.38	9.37	-2.82	0.005
HPP	-2.13	4.77	-0.45	0.655
LwL	-6.43	5.39	-1.19	0.233
SA	21.34	4.13	5.17	2e-07
Age	0.41	0.44	0.93	0.350
CondHT*Age	2.89	1.16	2.49	0.013
FC*Age	-0.21	0.65	-0.32	0.749
HPP*Age	0.97	0.72	1.36	0.174
LwL*Age	-0.55	0.80	-0.69	0.491
SA*Age	-0.25	0.90	-0.28	0.781

Table 4

Meta-analytic regression predicting effect size Cohen's d with participant age and method (central fixation is baseline method).

	Est. (CI)	SE	z	p
Intercept	0.285 [0.005,0.566]	0.14	2.00	0.05
Age	0.014 [0.002,0.026]	0.01	2.25	0.02
CondHT	1.284 [0.627,1.94]	0.34	3.83	0.00
FC	0.109 [-0.261,0.48]	0.19	0.58	0.56
HPP	0.125 [-0.043,0.293]	0.09	1.46	0.14
LwL	0.498 [0.071,0.925]	0.22	2.29	0.02
SA	-0.141 [-0.506,0.224]	0.19	-0.76	0.45
Age*CondHT	0.107 [-0.003,0.217]	0.06	1.91	0.06
Age*FC	0.044 [0.028,0.059]	0.01	5.51	0.00
Age*HPP	0.006 [-0.013,0.024]	0.01	0.60	0.55
Age*LwL	0.019 [-0.002,0.041]	0.01	1.80	0.07
Age*SA	-0.005 [-0.057,0.047]	0.03	-0.20	0.84

Table 5

Non-parametric correlations between sample sizes and effect sizes for each meta-analysis. A significant value indicates bias.

Meta-analysis	Kendall's Tau	p
Phonotactic learning	-0.21	0.052
Gaze following	0.09	0.512
IDS preference	0.01	0.921
Concept-label advantage	-0.06	0.59
Mutual exclusivity	-0.21	0.024
Native vowel discrim.	-0.28	< .001
Non-native vowel discrim.	-0.23	0.032
Pointing and vocabulary	-0.15	0.491
Sound symbolism	-0.04	0.698
Online word recognition	-0.13	0.539
Word segmentation	-0.10	0.023
Statistical sound learning	-0.06	0.724

Figure 1. Exclusion rate in percent by different methods. CF = central fixation, CondHT = conditioned headturn, FC = forced choice, HPP = headturn preference procedure, LwL = looking while listening, SA = stimulus alternation. Each point indicates a single study.

Figure 2. Effect size by different methods. CF = central fixation, CondHT = conditioned headturn, FC = forced choice, HPP = headturn preference procedure, LwL = looking while listening, SA = stimulus alternation. Each point indicates a single study.